

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis
hash://md5/619b6ef0f5984ac9a47a0661769e9515

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
review@globalbioticinteractions.org
<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis, has fingerprint hash://md5/619b6ef0f5984ac9a47a0661769e9515, is 581MiB in size and contains 191,252 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 8,967 primary taxa (e.g., *Augochlora pura*) and 7,912 associated taxa (e.g., *Prunus*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

ANSP-ENT | Academy of Natural Sciences Entomology Collection
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/ANSP-ENT_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z ASU-ASUCOB | Arizona State University Charles W. O'Brien Collection
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/ASU-ASUCOB_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z ASU-ROLS | Rick Overson and Laura Steger Invertebrate Observations
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/ASU-ROLS_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z CMNH-IZ | Carnegie Museum Invertebrate Zoology Collection
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/CMNH-IZ_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z DBG-DBGA | Denver Botanic Gardens Collection of Arthropods
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/DBG-DBGA_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z MAJC-INDD | Insect Diversity and Diagnostics Lab
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/MAJC-INDD_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z MSU-MSUC | The Albert J. Cook Arthropod Research Collection
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/MSU-MSUC_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z PSUC-ENTO | Frost Entomological Museum
https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/PSUC-ENTO_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z SLRC-SLRC |

Sangmi Lee Research Collection https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/SLRC-SLRC_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z SOAC-SOAC | Samanta Orellana Research Collection https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/SOAC-SOAC_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z TTU-TTU-Z | Museum at Texas Tech University Invertebrate Zoology Collection https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/TTU-TTU-Z_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z UTC-UTCI | University of Tennessee at Chattanooga Insect Collection https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/UTC-UTCI_DwC-A.zip 2026-06-02T14:48:30.977Z hash://md5/619b6ef0f5984ac9a47a0661769e9515

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 581MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis \
> review.tsv
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis`)

```

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv

```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that `data.zip` file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/ecdysis`, has fingerprint hash://md5/619b6ef0f5984ac9a47a0661769e9515, is 581MiB in size and contains 191,252 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., `interactsWith`) between 8,967 primary taxa (e.g., *Augochlora pura*) and 7,912 associated taxa (e.g., *Prunus*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Hesperotettix viridis viridis	adjacentTo	Alfalfa	https://ecdysis.org/collections/individual/index .
Hesperotettix viridis viridis	adjacentTo	Rabbit weed	https://ecdysis.org/collections/individual/index .
Hesperotettix viridis viridis	adjacentTo	Rabbit weed	https://ecdysis.org/collections/individual/index .
Hesperotettix viridis viridis	adjacentTo	Rabbit weed	https://ecdysis.org/collections/individual/index .

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
<code>interactsWith</code>	174768
<code>adjacentTo</code>	9252
<code>hasHost</code>	6860
<code>eats</code>	140

interactionTypeName	count
visitsFlowersOf	101
parasitoidOf	82
killedBy	31
visits	11
hostOf	5
parasiteOf	2

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Augochlora pura	12440
Ceratina calcarata	7037
Eucera hamata	6564
Heterodoxus spiniger	5598
Taenia pisiformis	5040
Bombus impatiens	3978
Arthropoda	3838
Apis mellifera	3469
Lasioglossum pilosum	3071
Melissodes bimaculatus	2829
Alaria marcianae	2701
Bombus vagans	2572
Agapostemon virescens	2569
Phthiraptera	2567
Aphididae	1601
Peponapis pruinosa	1402
Mesocestoides	1204
Taenia multiceps	1171
Taenia rileyi	1102

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Prunus	31379
Malus	23687
host	16659
Canis latrans (Canidae)	11333
male	2548

targetTaxonName	count
Agastache Blue Fortune	2226
female	1491
Canis latrans x rufus (Canidae)	1129
Mesquite	1039
Rudbeckia Herbstonne	989
ex. moist soil	973
Lynx rufus (Felidae)	880
Quercus	809
Agastache Black Adder	726
Peromyscus maniculatus	707
Picea abies	704
Sigmodon hispidus (Cricetidae)	703
Scapanus townsendii (Talpidae)	688
Felis rufus (Felidae)	668

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Augochlora pura	interactsWith	Malus	7157
Eucera hamata	interactsWith	Prunus	6279
Augochlora pura	interactsWith	Prunus	4327
Ceratina calcarata	interactsWith	Malus	3463
Ceratina calcarata	interactsWith	Prunus	3335
Heterodoxus spiniger	interactsWith	Canis latrans (Canidae)	2825
Lasioglossum pilosum	interactsWith	Prunus	2642
Taenia pisiformis	interactsWith	host	2345
Heterodoxus spiniger	interactsWith	male	2276
Agapostemon virescens	interactsWith	Prunus	2174
Melissodes bimaculatus	interactsWith	Prunus	2100
Bombus vagans	interactsWith	Malus	1714
Taenia pisiformis	interactsWith	Canis latrans (Canidae)	1672
Apis mellifera	interactsWith	Prunus	1612

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Alaria marciae	interactsWith	Canis latrans (Canidae)	1476
Bombus impatiens	interactsWith	Malus	1419
Bombus impatiens	interactsWith	Prunus	1244
Alaria marciae	interactsWith	host	1191
Apis mellifera	interactsWith	Malus	1132

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 4.780209265247716
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
```

```
        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
      END
    END
  END
END
```


Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Diaperis maculatus	SYNONYM_OF	col	Diaperis maculata
Diaprepes abbreviatus	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Diaprepes abbreviatus
Anobiidae	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Anobiidae
Dirabius rectirostris	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Dirabius rectirostris

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	6873
col	class	7
col	family	341
col	form	1
col	genus	1360
col	infraorder	2
col	infratribe	1
col	kingdom	2
col	order	29
col	parvorder	1
col	phylum	2
col	species	6216
col	subfamily	42
col	subgenus	57
col	suborder	7
col	subspecies	284
col	subterclass	1
col	subtribe	4
col	superfamily	6
col	superorder	2
col	tribe	22
col	variety	32
discoverlife	NA	14777
discoverlife	species	305
gbif	NA	6999
gbif	class	7

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
gbif	family	345
gbif	form	1
gbif	genus	1377
gbif	kingdom	3
gbif	order	29
gbif	phylum	2
gbif	species	6110
gbif	subspecies	302
gbif	variety	63
itis	NA	9292
itis	class	6
itis	division	1
itis	family	309
itis	genus	1023
itis	kingdom	2
itis	order	30
itis	phylum	1
itis	species	4172
itis	subclass	2
itis	subfamily	47
itis	subgenus	1
itis	subkingdom	1
itis	suborder	13
itis	subspecies	147
itis	superfamily	7
itis	superorder	4
itis	tribe	3
itis	variety	31
mdd	NA	15081
ncbi	NA	8963
ncbi	clade	3
ncbi	class	7
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	313
ncbi	genus	1178
ncbi	infraorder	1
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	28
ncbi	phylum	1
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	4426
ncbi	subclass	1
ncbi	subfamily	48
ncbi	subgenus	26

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
nbi	suborder	7
nbi	subspecies	74
nbi	subtribe	1
nbi	superfamily	7
nbi	superorder	4
nbi	tribe	4
nbi	varietas	9
pdb	NA	13574
pdb	class	6
pdb	family	241
pdb	genus	542
pdb	infraclass	1
pdb	infraorder	3
pdb	kingdom	2
pdb	order	36
pdb	phylum	2
pdb	species	617
pdb	subclass	2
pdb	subfamily	42
pdb	suborder	11
pdb	subspecies	2
pdb	subtribe	1
pdb	superfamily	7
pdb	superorder	2
pdb	tribe	5
pdb	unranked clade	5
tpt	NA	13729
tpt	family	17
tpt	genus	143
tpt	order	5
tpt	species	1185
tpt	specific epithet	1
tpt	subspecific epithet	3
wfo	NA	13662
wfo	family	12
wfo	genus	377
wfo	order	1
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	1004
wfo	subspecies	29
wfo	subtribe	1
wfo	variety	20
worms	NA	13161
worms	class	5

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	family	223
worms	genus	662
worms	infraorder	1
worms	kingdom	2
worms	order	26
worms	phylum	1
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	972
worms	subclass	3
worms	subfamily	3
worms	subgenus	2
worms	suborder	7
worms	subspecies	11
worms	subterclass	1
worms	subtribe	1
worms	superfamily	1
worms	superorder	2
worms	tribe	1
worms	variety	6

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	SYNONYM_OF	3681
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	9104
col	NONE	8158
discoverlife	NONE	17766
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	330
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	97
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	23
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	4012
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	9744
gbif	NONE	8254
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	6758
itis	NONE	10714
itis	SYNONYM_OF	794

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
mdd	NONE	17593
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	24
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	465
ncbi	NONE	10411
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	537
ncbi	SAME_AS	7269
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	14
pbdb	NONE	15810
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	230
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2160
tpt	NONE	16448
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1538
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	477
wfo	NONE	15906
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1917
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	545
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	234
worms	SYNONYM_OF	402
worms	NONE	15309
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2667

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
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Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
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2026-06-04T05:50:01Z	note	<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/ANSP- PARA_DwC-A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStu at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithF at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportD at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.revie at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.revie at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRu at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParam at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWrit at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java: at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java: 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjec at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine. 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(Command at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.ex 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(Command at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:1 at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java: Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca8346297446916617434tmp.zip] </pre>
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reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-04T05:50:01Z	note	<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/UASD- IIBZ-ENT- Odonata__DwC-A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStu at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(Da at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithF at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportD at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.revie at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.revie at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRu at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParar at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWrit at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java: at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java: 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObje at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine. 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(Comm at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.ex 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(Comm at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:1 at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java: Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca2826106055817369243tmp.zip] at </pre>

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-04T05:50:01Z	note	<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/AHAB_DwC- A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStu at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(Da at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithF at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportD at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRu at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParam at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWrit at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java: 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObject at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java: 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(Command at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(Command at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:1 at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java: Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca3228685286210361012tmp.zip] at org.globalbioticinteractions.dataset.DwCAUtil.archiveF at </pre>

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-04T05:50:01Z	note	<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/AZDA- AZDA-ENT__DwC- A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStu at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(Da at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithF at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportD at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRu at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParam at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWrit at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java: 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObject at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java: 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(Command at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(Command at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:1 at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java: Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca7184358885710586294tmp.zip] at org.globalbioticinteractions.dataset.DwCAUtil.archiveF </pre>

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

reviewComment	count
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Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
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<p> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/ANSP- PARA_DwC-A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:365) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:42) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:141) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithResolvedDependencies(DatasetImportUtil.java:97) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:88) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy(DatasetImporterForRSS.java:45) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review(CmdReview.java:259) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.reviewLocal(CmdReview.java:212) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRun(CmdReview.java:147) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParams.run(CmdDefaultParams.java:223) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWriterParams.run(CmdTabularWriterParams.java:12) at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java:1939) at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(<i>CommandLine.java</i> : 145)<i>atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjectOfLastSubcommandWithSameParent(CommandLine</i> at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(<i>CommandLine.java</i> : 2352)<i>atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java:2314)</i> at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute(<i>CommandLine.java</i> : 2179)<i>atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(CommandLine.java:2316)</i> at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(<i>CommandLine.java:2078</i>) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:110) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java:94) Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca8346297446916617434tmp.zip] at </p>	1
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reviewComment	count
<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/UASD- IIBZ-ENT-Odonata_DwC-A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:365) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:42) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:141) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithResolvedDependencies(DatasetImportUtil.java:97) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:88) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy(DatasetImporterForRSS.java:45) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review(CmdReview.java:259) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.reviewLocal(CmdReview.java:212) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRun(CmdReview.java:147) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParams.run(CmdDefaultParams.java:223) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWriterParams.run(CmdTabularWriterParams.java:12) at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java:1939) at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java : 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjectOfLastSubcommandWithSameParent(CommandLine at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java : 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java:2314) at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute(CommandLine.java : 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(CommandLine.java:2316) at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:110) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton26main(Elton.java:94) Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca2826106055817369243tmp.zip] at org.globalbioticinteractions.dataset.DwCAUtil.archiveFor(DwCAUtil.java:29) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:338) </pre>	1

reviewComment	count
<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/AHAB_DwC- A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:365) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:42) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:141) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithResolvedDependencies(DatasetImportUtil.java:97) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:88) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy(DatasetImporterForRSS.java:45) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review(CmdReview.java:259) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.reviewLocal(CmdReview.java:212) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRun(CmdReview.java:147) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParams.run(CmdDefaultParams.java:223) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWriterParams.run(CmdTabularWriterParams.java:12) at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java:1939) at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java : 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjectOfLastSubcommandWithSameParent(CommandLine at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java : 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java:2314) at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute(CommandLine.java : 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(CommandLine.java:2316) at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:110) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton27main(Elton.java:94) Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca3228685286210361012tmp.zip] at org.globalbioticinteractions.dataset.DwCAUtil.archiveFor(DwCAUtil.java:29) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:338) </pre>	1

reviewComment	count
<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [https://ecdysis.org/content/dwca/AZDA- AZDA-ENT_DwC-A.zip] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:365) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:42) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:141) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasetWithResolvedDependencies(DatasetImportUtil.java:97) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:88) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy(DatasetImporterForRSS.java:45) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review(CmdReview.java:259) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.reviewLocal(CmdReview.java:212) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRun(CmdReview.java:147) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParams.run(CmdDefaultParams.java:223) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWriterParams.run(CmdTabularWriterParams.java:12) at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java:1939) at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java : 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjectOfLastSubcommandWithSameParent(CommandLine at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java : 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java:2314) at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute(CommandLine.java : 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(CommandLine.java:2316) at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:110) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton28main(Elton.java:94) Caused by: java.io.IOException: failed to read [file:/tmp/dwca7184358885710586294tmp.zip] at org.globalbioticinteractions.dataset.DwCAUtil.archiveFor(DwCAUtil.java:29) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:338) </pre>	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-04) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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